

Infants' Defense Method (INDEM)

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Summary

During our childhood, even early after being borne, we have innate features for self-defense instinctively which are barely noticed. On the other hand, nowadays, martial arts and self-defense practices are being steadily educated as a popular form of training. These approaches can end up with consequences in real combats.

The purpose of the present paper is to introduce a new training concept by considering very basic and instinctive defensive movements exhibited by a human since his/her birth and develop and follow these features for self-defense in adolescence. This new concept will indicate that some martial arts (i.e. martial skills – different from common interpretation of a martial art) have been with us since our birth. Here we will demonstrate that even a cutie infant can provide us with noble self-defense ideas.

Introduction

Crying is the very first communication tool used by humans. Sense of hearing, smell, and seeing are significant means via which an infant tries to know his/her surrounding environment. Infants' hand movements are seemingly purposeless and unconscious unless to grab whatever touches their palms of hands, as is the case in monkeys as well. Baby monkeys have been observed to tend to grab and hang by their fathers' hair. As time passes, behaviors and hand movements become more and more purposeful. If a person gets close to an infant in a way that he/she feels uncomfortable, he/she will try to push away the disturber by his feet, which is the case in

cats too. However, if this action does not work, he/she will attempt to get rid of the disturber by successively hitting the predator on his/her face using his feet. He/she further tries to enter to a second phase of defense by screaming and using his/her hands as pawns – sharp nails make sense in this phase. Following the infancy and in the walking stage, self-defense procedures will be automatically shifted to initially screaming followed by hands stroking (throwing hands from sides). Kicking will be followed typically. By an age of 6 or 7, kicks will be transformed into foot-strokes where toes are thrown from sides. By the adolescence, this approach will be supplemented with head strokes, and the use of various tools. For example, you may get used to take advantage of your hands

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

and feet strokes in standing combats at first, but to proceed to grapple phase and then continue the fight on the ground. Nonetheless, in street fights, your rival may lay you down on the ground early, as can be seen in many cage competitions (pro-fighters in MMA championship have been trained for these situations).

Material and methods

One can establish a gender-based training methodology by statistically considering the defensive behavior exhibited by infants and children. Regardless of which martial arts a person is involved in, our proposed methodology is as follows:

Phase 1: Programming (training and nutrition)

In this phase, a training program will be designed (based on infant growth diagram, type of training and nutrition).

Phase 2: Mental preparation and senses enhancement (enhancing the five senses, concentrative training)

In this phase, based on purposes and training programs, concentrative exercises will be chosen or designed. Further concentrative exercises will be designed based on the five senses (particularly based on senses of hearing, seeing and touch) (evaluating the rival's energy through the sense of touch).

Phase 3: Breathing exercises and Kihop (Kiai)

In this phase, breathing exercises (especially abdominal breathing) will be chosen or designed. The following step will be to take *Kiai* exercises.

References

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Phase 3: Strengthening body via exercise

Based on infant's growth diagram, special programs will be designed for different parts of body.

Phase 4: Feedback of the last three phases (covering weaknesses and diagnosing strengths)

According to the schedule, trainees' programs will be checked by considering their strengths and weaknesses, with their programs being readjusted accordingly. This stage is also referred to as vaccination level. In this stage, trainees are required to perform one primitive form of practice.

Phase 5: Main exercises (at beginner and advanced levels)

Preferably, this phase should be started simultaneously with the other four phases. In this stage, the trainee begins to undertake exercises in lying position. Basic exercises include crawling, shuffling, tossing, and spinning as well as basic techniques. Advances exercises include self-defense techniques, feet kicks, sudden jumps, and relevant techniques.

Since this training approach is quite novel, we left with no chance to test it in practice. It is hoped that practical evaluation of and further research into this methodology can clarify other aspects of it, blowing a new spirit into the scope of self-defense and martial arts exercises. By paying attention to this concept and taking it seriously, one can build on main purpose and different aspects of this cognitive method.

Conclusion

This research has been compiled by based upon one of the author's personal experiences (the author's baby's behaviors) plus years of training in self-defense. As it has been already mentioned, the proposed training methodology included five phases, each of which having relevant sub-phases. For instance, Phase 3 dealt with KI (contemporary or constant) or Phase 5 includes exercises at two levels, namely beginner and advanced levels. Such an organized procedure tends to reactivate the process via which defense capabilities are formed, and makes all parts of body participating in the defense process. We suggest contemplating on such exercises. This method is called Infants' Defense Method – abbreviated as INDEM.